

FEATURES OF CHANGES IN LIPID AND CARBOHYDRATE METABOLISM IN PATIENTS WITH CORONARY HEART DISEASE AND DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract Dyslipidemia and hypertension are the most significant risk factors for the development of coronary artery disease and the earliest manifestations of metabolic disorders in patients with diabetes mellitus 2.

Key words: dyslipidemia, hypertension, dyslipidemia, type 2 diabetes.

The purpose of this work was to assess efficiency and safety drug Roxera in patients with type diabetes mellitus2 with dyslipidemia.

Materials and methods. We examined 30 patients with type 2 diabetes with confirmed dyslipidemia (LDL level < 2.6 mmol/l) Type II A (according to Fredrickson) Among them are 11 men and 15 women. The duration of the disease ranged from 2 year to 13 , average age $50,1 \pm 8,6$ years. There were also 10 practically healthy individuals were studied. 50,5% this group suffered from coronary artery disease, 90,1% from arterial hypertension. All patients underwent general clinical examination. Fasting and postprandial glycemia was studied by the glucose oxidase method.

Results. LDL level in the group with decompensated diabetes type 2 was 22.0% higher compared to compensated, and the HDL level is 19.5% lower in group with decompensated type 2 diabetes. Against the background of complex therapy, the patient was a daily single dose of the drug was prescribed Roxera at a dose of 10 mg for a month to achieve target blood lipid levels. Against the background ($P < 0.05$), at the beginning research, the latter was 2.85 ± 0.08 mmol/l, end of the period - 2.36 ± 0.036 mmol/l. During the period of treatment with Roxera, out of 30 patients examined, 10 (33.3%) reached target LDL treatment level detected lowering LDL levels with using drugs.

Conclusions

Thus, the opportunity to achieve the target LDL level in a short time during treatment with the drug. It is safety and good tolerability, and also a favorable cost/cost ratio efficiency" allows us to recommend it as one of the drugs of choice among hypocholesterolemic funds.

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